

Self-assembly of core-polyethylene glycol-lipid shell (CPLS) nanoparticles for drug delivery

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Abstract: Nanomaterials have revolutionized the delivery of therapeutics into cells. Therapeutic payloads ranging from small molecule drugs to antisense DNA and RNA cargoes have been effectively delivered into cells using a variety of nanoscale materials. Despite their promise and versatility, the effective delivery of exogenous biologically templated nanomaterials into cells is often thwarted by uptake into endosomes in cells. These vesicles are the natural response cells use to transport and compartmentalize materials entering a cell from the outside surroundings. As endosomes mature, they develop highly acidic conditions within their interior, and contain many degradation specific enzymes, including proteases and nucleases. When nanomaterials carrying therapeutic biomolecules are sequestered into endosomes, catalytic degradation often results coupled with the inability of the cargo to exist the endosome thus preventing it from reaching its intended target within the cell's cytosol. Our research seeks to rationally design lipid like vesicles around nanomaterials to form core-polyethylene glycol-lipid shell (CPLS) nanoparticles (NPs), as given in Fig. 1, in order to prevent the sequestration of their cargoes into vesicles and rather direct them into the cytosol of cells to achieve the most efficient delivery of their therapeutic payload.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of the self-assembly process for a CPLS NP. (b) Membrane fusion pathway for CPLS NP.

In our design, polyethylene glycol (PEG) polymers synthesized with one end of the PEG chain linked to a lipid (attached at the lipid head group) are covalently bound to the surface of an inorganic NP core. The NP core can be made of gold, silica, superparamagnetic iron oxide and many other nanomaterials. The particle can equally be considered as a PEGylated NP with all its terminal PEG chains bonded with lipid molecules (lipid heads). These lipids are denoted as 'anchored lipids'. In water, the PEGylated particles display the charged head groups of the anchored lipids to enhance their solubility. The addition of free lipids to the PEGylated particles induces the automatic absorption and formation of a lipid bilayer, due to the hydrophobic nature of the lipid tails, as long as a sufficient amount of free lipid molecules is added (cf. Fig. 1). In this way, a core-shell structure is built out from the inorganic NP core, where the PEG polymer is sandwiched between the core and the lipid bilayer shell. Within this core-PEG-lipid shell (CPLS) NP, the grafted PEG polymers support the bilayer. Therefore the proposed CPLS NP has the potential to be more stable than a traditional liposome. The distance between the core and the shell is constrained by the brush height of the tethered PEG polymers, giving rise to a more uniform and reproducible size of the self-assembled CPLS NPs. Moreover, upon interaction with the fluid like lipid bilayer of a cell membrane, there is a possibility for rearrangement of the lipids of both the shell of CPLS NPs and the cellular lipid bilayer, as the schematic shown in Fig. 1(b) depicts. During this rearrangement, the encapsulated therapeutic molecules can be directly delivered into the cytosol, bypassing the

endosome stage. Compared with liposomes, we *hypothesize* that the CPLS NPs would have the following advantages: (1) size uniformity due to the constraints applied through the grafting density and molecular weight of tethered PEG chain polymers; (2) enhanced stability due to the solid inorganic NP core and the covalent linking with PEG chains; (3) the potential for multifunctional properties, where the lipid vesicle can account for drug carrier capabilities and the inorganic NP core can be useful as a diagnostic imaging agent either as an optical tag or core for photothermal therapy; (4) high efficacy due to the membrane fusion pathway for directly delivering encapsulated therapeutics into the cytosol of diseases cells. To test the above hypothesis, *in silico* molecular simulations have been performed to study the self-assembly of optimized CPLS NPs and their interaction with cell membranes.

The self-assembly process of CPLS NPs is found to be sensitive to the grafting density and molecular weight of the tethered PEG chains, as well as the amount of free lipids added. At low grafting densities the assembly of CPLS nanoparticles cannot be accomplished. As demonstrated by simulations, a lipid bud/vesicle can be formed on the surface when an excess amount of free lipids is added at high grafting density. Therefore, the CPLS nanoparticles can only be formed under appropriate conditions of both PEG and free lipids. The CPLS nanoparticle has been recognized to be able to store a large quantity of water molecules, particularly with high molecular weight of PEG chains, indicating its capacity for carrying hydrophilic molecules such as therapeutic biomolecules or imaging agents. Under identical size and surface chemistry conditions of a liposome, it has been observed that the CPLS particle can be more efficiently wrapped by the lipid membrane, indicating its potential for a greater efficiency in delivering its hydrophilic cargo. As a proof-of-concept, the experimental realization of CPLS nanoparticles is explicitly demonstrated in this study. To test the capacity of the CPLS to store small molecule cargo a hydrophilic dye was successfully encapsulated in the particles' water soluble layer. The results of this study show the power and potential of simulation-driven approaches for guiding the design of more efficient nanomaterial delivery platforms.

The stability of CPLS nanoparticles in shear flow has also been systematically studied through large scale dissipative particle dynamics simulations. CPLS nanoparticles demonstrate higher stability and less deformation in shear flow, compared with lipid vesicles. Burst leakage of drug molecules inside lipid vesicles and CPLS NPs can be induced by the large pores at their tips. These pores are initiated by the maximum stress in the waist region. It further grows along with the tank-treading motion of vesicles or CPLS NPs in shear flow. However, due to the constraints applied by PEG polymers, CPLS NPs are less deformed than vesicles with comparable size under the same flow conditions. Thus, the less deformed CPLS NPs express a smaller maximum stress at waists, demonstrating higher stability. Pore formation at waists, evolving into large pores on vesicles, leads to the burst leakage of drug molecules and complete rupture of vesicles. In contrast, although similar drug leakage in CPLS nanoparticles can occur at high shear rates, pores initiated at moderate shear rates tend to be short-lived and close due to the constraints mediated by PEG polymers. This kind of 'self-healing' capability can be observed over a wide range of shear rates for CPLS nanoparticles. Our results suggest self-assembled CPLS nanoparticles to exhibit high stability during blood circulation without rapid drug leakage. These features make CPLS nanoparticles candidates for a promising drug delivery platform.